
A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE HISTORY OF NEWSPAPER PRESS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study adopted the historical study design and anchored on modernization and global media theories to critically examine the stated objective for establishing Iwe Irohin, the first newspaper published in Nigeria. The study explored other influences which were not apparent in the face of the objective realities that provided impetus for the publisher, Rev. Townsend, to start a newspaper at the time he did at Abeokuta (Nigeria), including their consequences on the newspaper press that emerged afterward. Study objectives include: to understand the “other” motivations for Townsend to arrive Abeokuta to establish a newspaper in 1859 (order than to “get the people to read and to beget the habit of seeking information through reading”); to understand how the context within which Townsend composed his motive provided impetus for him; to find out the consequences of Townsend’s motive and the context in which it was composed on the structure and performance of the newspaper press that emerged in its stead. The study relied on the data obtained from secondary sources, analyzed via narrative interpretation method and argued that Townsend’s belief was ethnocentric and his statement ideological. The study therefore concludes that the motive of the forerunner of the newspaper press in Nigeria was not altruistic as we were meant to believe, but was a function of a prevalent western socio-economic and ideological background (the context within which he was born and raised). Hence the newspaper press that emerged in its stead became not developmental in structure and performance, but reactionary, as the petite bourgeoisie proprietors aspired not to recover and steer the traditional society on the road to sustainable development, but rather to participate and carve a niche in the imperialist expansionist project that followed.*

Keywords: History. Ideology. Development. Newspaper. Nigeria.

Introduction

Background

Two European adventurers, Rev. Henry Townsend of the Church Missionary Society (CMS) based in

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Abeokuta and Rev. Hope Waddle of the Presbyterian Church of Scotland Mission based in Calabar, were said to be instrumental to the origin and evolution of the newspaper press in Nigeria (Sunday, 2008). Townsend and Waddle introduced the printing press, the technology that made newspaper press possible in Nigerian (Ajibade, 2003; Sobowale, 1985). Meanwhile, on the global scale, the technology of printing and the use of movable type were known and applied in China and Korea long before Johannes Gutenberg who was credited as the German inventor in the mid-fifteenth century (McQuail, 2010, pg.25).

While Ajibade (2003) and Sunday (2008) have it that Townsend came to Abeokuta in December 1842 and seventeen years later published Iwe Irohin, the first newspaper in Nigeria, Sunday (2008, Pg. 11-12) records that Iwe Irohin, was in vernacular and essentially a Christian religious newspaper, but had its news coverage broadened to include commercial news about prices of agricultural products (especially palm oil); announcements from local chiefs and from the government of Lagos Colony. Furthermore, Duyile (1987) and Coker (1971) show that the newspaper also denounced the evils of slave trade, but that Townsend's later deep involvement in Abeokuta politics invariably accounted for the demise of Iwe Irohin in 1867.

It is significant to observe that Sunday (2008) recorded that when Townsend was asked what actually motivated him to come to Abeokuta at the time he did, with a printing press, and what made him to start a newspaper. To this question, Coker (1968) quoted Townsend to have said:

“My objective is to get the people to read, that is, to beget the habit of seeking information through reading.”

The above scenario marked the beginning of a newspaper industry in Abeokuta, that was about the period (1861) when the British administration formally commenced with the ceding of Lagos and the territory which later became Nigeria to the “Crown”, an area that lies at the extreme inner corner of the Gulf of Guinea in West Africa (Coleman, 1958).

Statement of the problem and method of study

Chinweizu (1978) showed that there existed some hidden pre-colonial social forces that gave rise to Europe's colonization of Africa. These social forces largely motivated and influenced western colonial adventurism in Africa. Hence, this study examines the ideological predispositions that motivated the establishment of Iwe Irohin, which no doubt seemed to have had consequences for the structure and performance of the newspaper press that later emerged in its stead. The study assumes that the predisposition which helped to establish and shape newspaper journalism in Nigeria was no doubt much more than to “to get the people to beget the habit of seeking information through reading”. There seemed to be a transplanting of an ideology and its material culture, an imposition of a false paradigm with little or no consideration for its consequences on the then would be Nigerian social formation at a critical stage of its development. Townsend's narrative as chronicled cannot be accepted without being thoroughly subjected to critical analysis (Ibraheem, 2015).

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The study hence adopted the historical study design, obtained data from secondary sources and used the narrative interpretation method of data analysis to critically examine Rev. Townsend's stated objective for establishing the first newspaper in Nigeria in the face of the pre-colonial objective conditions/realities that provided impetus for him to start a newspaper at the time he did at Abeokuta. The study is an attempt to bridge a gap in knowledge and to document a conceptual, critical and humanist reconstruction and re-interpretation of the stated motive of the forerunner of the newspaper press in Nigeria. This re-interpretation is necessary considering the need for proper understanding and for community engagements in identifying issues and defining options for actions.

Objectives of study

The general objective of this study is to re-construct and re-interpret the narrative of Rev. Townsend (the forerunner of the newspaper press in Nigeria) in the light of the pre-colonial objective conditions/realities that existed and provided impetus for him to establish a newspaper at a time he did at Abeokuta.

The specific objectives of the study include:

1. To understand the other social forces that was not apparent but motivated Townsend to arrive Abeokuta to establish a newspaper in 1859.
2. To understand how the context in which Townsend's motive was composed provided impetus for him.
3. To find out the consequences which the context Townsend's motive was composed have on the structure and performance of the newspaper press that emerged in its stead.

Research questions:

1. What other social forces that were not apparent motivated Townsend to arrive Abeokuta to establish a newspaper in 1859?
2. How do the context and objective conditions in which Townsend's motive was composed provided impetus for him?
3. What consequences do Townsend's context in which his motive was composed have on the structure and performance of the newspaper press that emerged afterward?

Review of related literature

Ideology

Conceptual clarifications for ideology and predisposition could be many and varied. Ideology denotes a set of beliefs, especially political beliefs on which people, parties and countries base their actions (BBC English Dictionary). Agbanu (2013, Pg. 112-115) states however, that peoples' belief system is a function of the knowledge/information they hold about their environment, right or wrong and has a direct link to their attitude and by extension their actions. Similarly, Hall (2003) uses the term Ideology to refer to those images, concepts, and premises which provide the frameworks through which people represent, interpret, understand and "make sense" of some aspects of their social

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existence. This author further states that there is close relationship between the media and ideology, arguing that media function touches directly the problem of ideology, since the media's main sphere of operation is the production and transformation of ideologies. For Hall (2003) therefore, "an intervention in the media's construction of issues in society is an intervention in the ideological terrain of struggle". Hence Hall (2003) noted three important things about ideology, namely:

(1) That ideologies do not exist as isolated and separate concepts, but exist in the construction of different elements into a distinctive set of meanings. Hence ideological struggle and transformation take place in many ways including articulating its elements differently within deferent contexts, thereby producing a different meaning. This means that a concept can be made to have different meanings within the logic of different ideological discourses and social practices. Using the concept of freedom as an example Hall states that the concept of "freedom" is connected to individualism and free market in liberal democracies, while in socialist ideology the same concept is seen as a collective condition which may not include equality (Hall, 2003).

(2) That although individuals make ideological statements, ideologies are not the product of the individual's consciousness or intention. Rather individuals formulate their intentions, produce their social consciousness and make sense of social relations within ideology. Ideologies hence pre-date individuals and form part of the determinate social formations and conditions in which the individuals are born and exist (Hall, 2003).

(3) That ideologies work by constructing for both the individual and the collective, positions of identification and knowledge which allow them to proclaim ideological truths as if they are the authentic authors. This according to Hall (2003) is not because they come out from their innermost, authentic and unified experience but because they find themselves mirrored in the positions at the center of the social practices from which the statements they formulate "make sense". Nonetheless, Hall (2003) identifies the media as the apparatuses which generate and circulate ideologies and that in modern societies the different media are important sites for the production, reproduction and transformation of ideologies.

For Marx and Engels (Lenin 1965), ideology has both political and economic interfaces with economic pursuit determining the direction of politics and actions of men. The authors believe that capitalism, the dominant mode of production in the west, is a form of political ideology consisting of an economic activity that encourages individualism and private ownership of the means of production. Private ownership of means of production according to them creates a class society where the relationship of production is that of class conflict, due to internal contradictions of the capitalist mode of production. This internal dialectics according to Lenin (1965) reached a stage where the surplus values appropriated as profits by the dominant class became merchant/finance capital seeking a more profitable investment opportunities abroad. Chinweizu (1978) and Lenin (1965) state that the export/investment of merchant/finance capital resulted in imperialism and colonization of less

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endowed climes, the highest stage of capitalism (V.I. Lenin, Collected works, vol. 22, pg. 226). This period of western expansionism was said to have provided impetus for adventurers and explorers of the western stock (including Townsend) the opportunity to venture out and dominate other less endowed climes (Lenin, *ibid*).

Predisposition

Sietel (2004) described Predispositions as attitudes which are generally assumed to be judgments or evaluations people make about specific issues, their feelings or predispositions to think in a certain way about a certain topic. Attitude on certain issues according to the author are determined by certain factors, including personal, cultural, educational, family, religion, social class and race. These characteristics help to influence the formation of attitude, so do other factors such as experience, economic status, political and organizational membership. Again Sietel (2004) says that attitude and behavior are situational (context driven). They are influenced by specific issues in specific situations. Nevertheless, when others with similar attitude reach similar consensus, public opinion is born. Public opinion is an indicator of perception and attitude (meaning) people have about an issue, which help determine their actions. Meaning as have been shown by Hall (2003) is in the domain of ideology.

The newspaper press

Amobi and McAdams (2014) states that Newspaper is an aspect of the mass media outside of television, radio, cinema and the internet and along with other printed matters is referred to as the press, taken from its major technology, the printing press. Similarly, Vivian (2005) records that Johannes Guttenberg invented the movable type in the 1450s and this revolutionized printing by making printing of multiple copies at the same time possible. However with the advent of digitization, media convergence became common place as digitalization made online/multimedia publishing possible. This according Amobi and McAdams (2014) has prompted newspaper publishing in either hard or soft copy editions or both alongside video, audio and graphic contents, on online multimedia platforms on the World Wide Web.

McQuail (2010) states that Newspaper was an urban phenomenon and that it debuted in the seventeen century as an extension into the public domain of an activity that had long taken place for governmental, diplomatic, commercial and private purposes. The early newspaper according to this author was marked by its regular appearance, commercial interest and public character and was used for information, record, advertising, diversion and gossip. Newspapers according to McQuail (2010) consequently evolved with social, political, and economic development of societies, with partisan, elite, and popular newspapers playing various vital social, political and economic roles for the society. Furthermore, McQuail (2010) states that before newspapers started in Europe in the 19th century news was limited to reports of events that relate to commerce, hence the origin of news lies with the activities of traders and that is why the evolution of news agencies can be traced to activities related to

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trade and commerce. To this effect Ibraheem (2015) states:

...” in addition to trade and commerce, government was one institution that promoted news, not through newspapers, but through the sending of newsletters to diplomatic missions, but in the 19th century the coming of Industrial revolution created an urban middle class with new jobs and income, whose social demands led to the development of elite newspapers. There was then no platform for this new urban group to aggregate and express their views. Newspapers came up as platforms for aggregation of views of the middle class. The urban middle class in Europe at that time gathered at coffee houses or cafés. These coffee houses accordingly became platforms for discussions about events and issues in society and were referred to as public spheres”.

Harbamas (1989) described public sphere as a forum where people meet to discuss the affairs of the society and where opinions are formed and those opinions are carried by newspapers.

Citing Hughes (1940), McQuail (2010) says that the press has always specialized in human interest stories, in dramatic and sensational styles of reporting and presentation. Okoye, (2007) hence says that societies, especially democratic ones for this reason began to assign sacred roles, such as monitoring governance, and holding government accountable and responsible to the people through their reportage. And that in creditably performing this function that newspapers and other news media impact the society, creating awareness and raising peoples’ consciousness about events and issues in their environments, nationally and globally.

Theoretical framework

1. World system theory

According to Ezeoke and Asak (2018), World system or Global media system theory propounded by Wallerstein in 1974, stipulates that all nations are shaped by the larger systems to which they belong and that in the international system, political, economic and cultural powers flow from the core nations to the periphery. Both core and peripheral nations are always “working or struggling” within a global system to maximize production. Commenting on the world media system theory, McQuail (2010, pg. 251) says that there is no formal arrangement of the global media structure beyond the national frontiers, although many separate sovereign states interact and communicate, but that the pathways of flow and exchange between nations follow some regular and predictable (although changing) patterns and this help to visualize a structure of a kind.

Modernization theory

Anaeto, et. al. (2008) has stated that modernization theory propounded by Max Weber assumes that modernity is a function of the institutionalization of rationality among the target population which results in social specialization and bureaucratization of the society. Again the authors say that modernization in an emerging culture is based on a scientific and rational outlook and the application in all spheres of life some higher level of technology as evolution in culture. According to Waisebord (2001) modernization theory also assumes that the problems of development and social change in the

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post-war world were due to lack of progress equivalent to western countries, and that the problems were basically rooted in lack of knowledge (information and understanding) in the population. Consequently intervention was needed to provide people with information to change unacceptable behaviors/practices. Waisebord (2001) stated further that because the problem of underdeveloped regions was believed to be an information problem, communication was presented as the instrument that would solve it. This invariably informed Townsend's idea of establishing a printing press to help the people "beget information through reading". This position is supported by Lerner (1958) and Schramm (1964), for whom communication basically meant the transmission of information and perhaps persuasion as formulated by Aristotle in his Rhetoric as stated in Dissayanake (2000). For these studies, exposure to mass media was one of the factors among others (e.g. urbanization, literacy, secularization and industrialization) that could bring modern attitudes among backward population such as Abeokuta at the time Townsend came calling.

Literature gap

Literature on the history of mass media in Nigeria especially on the history of the newspaper press chronicled impressive accounts of the origin of mass media and the newspaper press in Nigeria. However, none of these works offered a humanist reconstruction/re-interpretation of the historical facts by critically analyzing the ideological predispositions that informed the context within which the idea of introducing a newspaper press by Townsend was composed. This is the gap in literature that this study attempts to bridge.

Methodology

This study adopts the historical study method. Historical method of inquiry uses abstractions from secondary data or interrogations or both to obtain data from available sources for critical analyses. Again historical study method works with primary documents, records, and artifacts (Tejumaye, 2003, pg.12), and seeks to collect testimonies from authorities or others who can support or disconfirm written and media materials. This entails drawing conclusions and presenting new explanations about past communication events and communicators (Rubin, et.al, 2005).

This study therefore brings both humanist and critical perspectives to bear on its subject of inquiry by attempting to reinterpret the contexts (i.e. the Western intellectual Socio-cultural and traditional African milieu) within which Townsend originally composed his thought.

Again the study uses the narrative interpretation approach to data analysis. It is a qualitative research analytical approach that has been accepted in the social science research circle, and operates from an "interpretative stand point". Qualitative studies do not search for the truth, but offer "truthful explanations to everyday living" (Odotola, 2014).

Presentation and Analysis of Data and Answers to Research question.

RQ 1: What other social forces that was not apparent motivated Townsend to arrive Abeokuta to establish a newspaper in 1859?

Townsend's stated intention which was to "get the people to read and to beget the habit of seeking information through reading", seemed innocuous, morally upright and altruistic. However, it was only a function of his ideological predisposition. In this respect his statement was intrinsically ideological and ethnocentric. The ethnocentric nature and ideological position of Townsend's intention might not have been seen on the surface even by him, but they were real and nonetheless rooted in his consciousness. This assertion is in line with the submissions of Hall (2003) on the nature of ideology. The ethnocentric posture of Townsend's statement was a function of his consciousness that had roots in the Western socio-cultural context (Chinweizu, 1978 and Lenin, 1965). This context was typified by the acclaimed western liberal social science's "cultural superiority" and "modernization" paradigm that targeted the so called "backward traditional societies" (Lerner, 1958; Rostow, 1960, Pye, 1963; and Schramm, 1964). Thus Townsend, as a Christian missionary of the CMS hue, came with this background of western social science scholarship which held a great influence on his world view. This informed his idea of "getting them to beget the habit of getting information through reading". The traditional societies such as Abeokuta were backward because they lacked western information was a classical western liberal social scientific conclusion (Ake, 2009; Waisebord, 2001).

It is important to note that Townsend was shown to have been born and nurtured in Scotland (Sunday, 2008), within the dominant capitalist ideology of the west. This ideology had produced his consciousness and intention. Having come from this background and influenced by its contradictory and exploitative mode of social production, Townsend's consciousness and predisposition which produced his intention was not actually born out of his love and concern for Abeokuta social formation. He only formulated his intention, produced his social consciousness and made sense of Abeokuta social formation within the western ideology (Hall, 2003). Ideologies according to Hall (2003) pre-date individuals and form part of the determinate social formations and conditions in which the individuals are born and exist. This indicates that Townsend was making a statement out of a consciousness and predisposition acquired from and influenced by an ideology which predated him and which formed part of the western social formation and conditions in which he was born. So to create in the people the habit of seeking information through reading, by establishing a newspaper press, proclaimed a hidden ideological truth and connotes a form of literacy campaign he aimed at providing the people with information seeking habit that he hoped would affect the relatively backward behaviors found in the "traditional culture" that was Abeokuta. It could also be literally interpreted to mean that Townsend believed (in line with the then prevailing development paradigm

of the western social science scholarship) that the people and the society he met typified by Abeokuta were traditional and backward because they lack information and modernization (Waisebord 2009). Consequently, if armed with a modern technology of the printing press and perhaps the establishment of the newspaper press (a mass communication medium) the ‘traditional people’ would be helped to acquire the basic communication skill of reading and begetting information through reading. If these people would acquire this skill, Townsend had hoped the ‘traditional people’ would not only be able to acquire and interpret information, but would also become ‘modern and developed; that is be able to think and behave like the west, where he (Townsend) came from. This nonetheless mirrored the position at the center of the social context and practices from which the statement Townsend composed “make sense”, a position of cultural superiority.

As indicated by Hall (2003), ideologies work by constructing for both the individual and the collective, positions of identification and knowledge which allow them to proclaim ideological truths as if they are the authentic authors, because they find themselves mirrored in the positions at the center of the social context and practices from which the statements they formulate “make sense”. To get the people to read and to beget information through reading is a constructed position occasioned by identification and knowledge that allowed Townsend to proclaim an ideological truth as if he was the authentic author and as if it came out from his innermost, authentic experience. Townsend’s intention made sense only in the context of Western capitalist ideology within which he was raised. Hall (2003) identifies the media as the apparatuses which generate and circulate ideologies and that in modern societies the different media are important sites for the production, reproduction and transformation of ideologies. So establishing Iwe irohin was a very important watershed in integrating the Abaokuta traditional socio-cultural milieu into the capitalist ideology of the west, an objective that was not apparent to Townsend.

RQ 2: How does the context in which Townsend’s motive was composed provided impetus for him?

The capitalist mode of production, its internal contradictions and international expansionism provided the impetus for, and the objective reality, the socio-cultural context, in which Townsend composed his narrative. We have argued before now, that although it seemed not so apparent, Townsend’s motive (embedded in his consciousness and predisposition) was a function of the western philosophical and socio-cultural context in which he was raised. This socio-cultural context seemed to have the goal to “modernize” the so called “Dark continents”, but obviously undertook a task that explored, conquered and exploited” (Ake, 1983, 2009). This fact was not apparent to Townsend, but, no doubt informed his predisposition and intention to arrive Abeokuta with his Printing press.

Townsend was knowingly and unknowingly reacting to the forces of the dominant capitalist ideology in Europe at the time he arrived Abeokuta. At the time Townsend came calling with the technology of the printing press, capitalism had developed to the stage of imperialism (Lenin, 1965: Collected

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Works). Technological transfer to societies that lack it was an important part of the modernization paradigm. Pye (1963) has spoken of modernization in an emerging culture as based on a scientific and rational outlook and the application in all spheres of life some higher level of technology. As it has been shown in development literature, modernization proponents assume that the problems of development and social change in the post-war world were due to lack of progress equivalent to western countries, and that the problems were basically rooted in lack of knowledge/information in the population (Waisebord, 2001). Consequently intervention was needed to provide the people with information to change unwanted behaviors.

Following the above line of thought Waisebord (2001) says that for Western Liberal Social scientists, to solve these problems require instilling modern values and information through the transfer of media technology and the adoption of innovation and culture originated in the west. The period in time when Townsend arrived Abeokuta with the technology of the printing press corresponded to a stage in the development of capitalism when European local labours and raw materials were no longer adequate to sustain the emerging factories. It was a stage when adventurers and venture (finance) capitalists moved out of the west to seek new markets and to conquer new lands for raw materials and labour for the European factories, occasioned by Industrial revolution. (Wallerstain 1974; McQuail, 2010; Chinweizu, 1978).

Three strategies were available for the capitalist expansionist's mission, namely: military conquest (gun- boat diplomacy), Christianity, and western education (Chinweizu, 1978).

Being of the Christian faith, Townsend armed with the two of these tools of capitalist conquest namely: Christianity and education (printing press being an accessory) arrived Abeokuta in 1842. Within the ambit of this capitalist ideology and its imperialist extension (colonialism), Townsend founded Iwe irohin and introduced newspaper press into Abeokuta or rather into the territory known as the Oil River Protectorate of the Royal Niger Company which later became Nigeria (Coleman 1958).

RQ 3: What consequences do Townsend's context in which his motive was composed have on the structure and performance of the newspaper press that emerged afterward?

Townsend's intention to instill in the people the habit of seeking information through reading and the western capitalist socio-cultural context in which he composed this narrative had lots of consequences on the structure and performance of the newspaper press that emerged in their stead. One of the most striking consequences is that the newspapers from Iwe irohin (1859) to the others that came after it, up till independence in 1960 and beyond, did not seek to change the society fundamentally. They became not developmental in structure and performance, but reactionary as the petite bourgeoisie proprietors aspired not to recover and steer the traditional society on the road to sustainable development, but rather to participate and carve a niche in the imperialist expansionist project that followed.

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They mainly sought to carve a profitable niche within the colonial state, for their owners and the social class they belonged to. The elitist newspaper owners who were aware of the so called principles of individualism, liberty and egalitarianism of the west wished simply to be accommodated within the tenets of the prevailing capitalist mode of production. They had no intention of ideologically changing the status quo, but to participate in it, as equal partners in the imperialists' colonial project (Chinweizu, 1978).

This group of locals had been exposed to the ideals and practices of capitalism as they were educated and enlightened only to the extent of being conscious of the reality of the positions they occupy in the emerging capitalist formation. But the position this class occupied had neither economic nor political base. Hence their actions were reactionary: agitate for political independence through nationalism, in the hope that political independence will usher in economic independence.

Sunday (2008) identified three significant epochs in the emergence and evolution of the newspaper press in Nigeria, namely: the Religious era, the Nationalist era and the Post-Independence era. The Religious era began with Iwe Iroyin as the first newspaper that was ever published in Nigeria, with essentially a religious thrust (Sunday 2008). It was followed closely by other newspapers that had different missions. Because these newspapers were informed by the tenets of the capitalist mode of production they had structures and performances that were influenced by the normative libertarian theory of the press that was prevalent at the turn of the 19th century. As a newspaper Iwe Irohin may not be described as a public sphere as was conceptualized by Habermas (1989), neither did it create one for public discussions and public opinion formations. This perhaps, could be because there were no factories and factory workers that could have constituted a new industrial urban middle class at Abeokuta, as was the case in the west during the industrial revolution. The presence of industrial middle class helped the early newspapers in Europe to emerge as public spheres (McQuail 2010). Iwe Irohin was a transmission/top down communication model and at best embodied the elements of the publicity communication model for it carried advertisements for churches, colonial administration and businesses (Sunday, 2008). So long as it maintained this thrust, Iwe Iroyin did well in the eyes of the prevailing power elites. However, Coker (1968) speculated that Iwe Iroyin in the last three years of its existence entered into the web of Egba political crisis and seized publication amidst the ensuing confusion. Invariably, Iwe Iroyin's demise followed the pattern observed by McQuail (2010) that early newspapers reported trade and commerce and so long as they maintained this seemingly innocuous commercial thrust without veering into reporting politics, they published without let or hindrance and without conflicts with the state.

Robert Campbell founded the Anglo African newspaper on December 30th 1865. This marked the beginning of the secular era of newspaper press (Sunday 2008). Campbell a West Indian businessman who settled in Nigeria no doubt had the Western capitalist orientation. His newspaper according to Sunday (2008) was a reaction to the political and internal contradictions of the colonial reality and

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lasted for only two years and six months. This again mirrored the same pattern that newspapers get into troubled waters when they report and comment on political matters of the day. Consequently, for the next 13 years (1867 – 1880) as Sunday (2008) recorded, “black period” resulted in the evolution of newspaper journalism in Nigeria.

Lagos Times, published by Richard Beale Blaize appeared in 1880 and signaled the beginning of another era, the nationalist era in Nigeria newspaper press (Sunday 2008). This era had a robust background in socio-political and economic influences of the capitalist west. Social precedents that were set during the missionary era and the educational programmes of the missionaries had produced a literate group among the populace, most of them molded on the tenets of capitalist ideology. Certain social, political and economic developments such as partitioning of Africa (1870 - 1880), interacted with the impacts of local and external sources of inspiration to create conditions which favored the emergence of popular newspapers (Sunday,2008). Partitioning of the African continent among the big nations was another agonizing vestige of the capitalist ideology. By this time the frustrations of the educated Africans which had been gathering momentum since the 1860s gradually got to a climax. As a result, Lagos Times and other newspapers established in the closing years of the 19th century, including Lagos observer, the Eagle, Iwe Irohin Eko, Lagos standard and Lagos echo, joined in the emerging fire of nationalism (Sunday,2008).

The point that must be made which is most relevant to this discuss is that all the newspapers were set up by the descendant of freed slaves, who came from Sierra Leone, most of whom were businessmen. These businessmen/publishers brought to bear on their publications the orientations they received in capitalist ideology and were influenced by the principles of individualism and libertarianism as it were. In so doing they inadvertently extended the social principles of the capitalist ideology to the traditional society. To buttress this position, Sunday (2008) said that these descendants of freed slaves having been schooled in the tenets of capitalism and libertarianism started to express nationalist sentiments characterized by calls for self-rule and pungent criticisms of British colonial administration. The significance of this development was that at this time the newspapers had become a real public sphere in the mold of Herbamas (1989). However, the colonial government checkmated the newspapers in various ways including violence, little or no advertising patronage, and obnoxious laws. Nevertheless, a group of locals had been exposed to the ideals and practices of capitalism and were educated and enlightened only to the extent of being conscious of the reality of the non-economic positions they occupy in the emerging capitalist formation. The only option was to agitate for political independence, through nationalist struggle, in the hope that political independence will usher in economic independence. This was the pattern till independence in 1960 (Sunday, 2008).

This emergent powerless class saw newspaper press as a viable tool for political and economic struggle. The “Printing press” the media technology available at the time reached out and influenced

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public opinion of the day. The Weekly record newspaper edited by John Payne Jackson and later his Son, Heratio Jackson pioneered this era. But the main nationalist newspaper press of 1880 - 1960 was controlled by Nigerians who became more involved in politics. With their newspapers the owners/journalists/politicians instigated Nigerians into staging protests including sending delegations to government houses, mass rallies in cities and towns, to denounce bad colonial policies (Sunday, 2008). In this way newspaper press became a tool for political agitation in the hands of nationalist politicians. Politicians like Christopher Kumolu Johnson, established and used the Nigerian chronicle in 1908, Mr. Separa William co-founded and used Nigerian Times in 1910, while Ajasa Akitoye founded and used Nigeria Pioneer in 1914, but used it more as a public relations tool for the colonial government (Sunday,2008).

Newspaper press under the auspices of the nationalists took a vibrant dimension with the entrance of African messenger in 1921 by Ernest Ikoli, Lagos Daily News (1925) by Herbert Macaulay, Daily Times 1926 by the Nigerian Printing and publishing company. Other newspapers that showed vibrancy were West African Pilot (1937) by Nnamdi Azikiwe, Nigerian Tribune (1949) by Obafemi Awolowo. All these newspapers and journalist were politicians and some of them founded political parties. They also constituted the bulk of Nigerians that took over the realms of power at independence in 1960.

The ideology that these political-journalists inherited that informed and influenced the operations, structures and performances of their newspapers was the capitalist ideology. But the social status of these political-journalists in the capitalist formation was that of an educated class that lacked both political and economic base. The colonial economic base as well as its political infrastructure was effectively controlled by the international capitalist system. The colonies were just the periphery and the extension of the Western capitalist ideology. The nationalists only employed newspaper press to secure a place within the capitalist formation, but not to overthrow it. The consequence was enthroning to a large extent a reactionary variant of the newspaper press in Nigeria. When the nationalists eventually took over the realm of political power in 1960, the struggle shifted focus from being a struggle against colonialism and for fundamental social change, to inter-ethnic struggle for domination. The politicians who owned the newspapers began to appeal to ethnic sentiments to acquire political powers and to build both political and economic bases for themselves. Nnamdi Azikiwe deployed his "African pilot" to the cause of his political empire along the line of his Igbo dominated South-east. Obafemi Awolowo was not left out in deploying the "Tribune Newspaper" group to achieve a similar purpose along the line of his Yoruba dominated South-west. Ahmadu Bello did not waste time in establishing "The New Nigeria Newspaper" to champion the cause of ethnic Hausa-Fulani dominated north.

The struggle for political power became an ultimate struggle for controlling the apparatuses of the state which became synonymous with controlling the resources of the state, as the colonial and post-colonial states had become means of production and appropriators of surplus values (Eme Ekekwe,

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1986).

Conclusions

This study concludes that the motive for establishing the newspaper press (Iwe Iroyin) in Abeokuta in 1859, “to make the people to beget the habit of getting information through reading”, was a function of a western imperialist ideological and ethnocentric predisposition. The motive was informed by the liberal social scientific paradigm that was rooted in the capitalist ideology of the west. Although the motive seemed innocuous and altruistic, there were hidden intrinsic forces that informed the actor’s consciousness and predisposition. This ideology ultimately shaped the evolution, nature and performance of the newspaper press that was to emerge in Nigeria- a reactionary press.

Recommendations

This study therefore recommends as follows:

1. That citizens of a nation be trained in the art of critical thinking to be able to discern the hidden meanings and motives of the significant others that they are dealing with, no matter how superior, altruistic, selfless and well-meaning the significant others may seem to be.
2. Profit making and appropriation of surplus values should not be the sole motive for establishing and operating media business. People’s welfare should be top on the agenda.
3. That structures and performances of emerging newspaper press be influenced not only by the authoritarian and libertarian principles but by the social responsibility and social development theories of the press.
4. Newspaper press should be conceptualized as public sphere, a space of information, communication and opinion formation. This will help to produce and channel criticisms and commentaries necessary for fundamental changes in society.
5. Further studies in interpretive analysis, humanist and critical perspective should be carried out to reconstruct the context in which most original works were composed to help disconfirm certain entrenched assertions such as that made by the likes of Rev. Townsend.

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